

A Graph Neural Network-Based Framework for Reliability Prediction of Automated Carotid Intima-Media Thickness Segmentation

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases remain the leading cause of global mortality. Carotid intima-media thickness (CIMT) is a well-established surrogate biomarker for early atherosclerosis detection. Manual CIMT ultrasound segmentations are more time-consuming and prone to error than automated CIMT ultrasound segmentations. This study presents a two-stage framework that integrates metric-based evaluation with Graph Neural Network (GNN)-based learning for automated CIMT segmentation evaluation and reliability prediction. In the first stage, segmentation performance was evaluated using overlap-based metrics, including the Dice Similarity Coefficient (*DSC*) and Jaccard Index (*JI*), together with the distance-based Point-to-Distance Metric (*PDM*). In the second stage, a GNN was trained on a patient similarity graph constructed from aggregated clinical features and segmentation-derived metrics for patient-level segmentation reliability prediction. The metric-based evaluation yielded a mean *DSC* of 0.915 ± 0.143 , a mean *JI* of 0.863 ± 0.158 , and *PDM* values of 0.239 ± 0.070 mm and 0.236 ± 0.067 mm for the Lumen–Intima and Media–Adventitia boundaries, respectively, indicating close agreement between automated and manual segmentations. The GNN-based learning achieved a Pearson’s correlation coefficient (*r*) of 0.972 with a Mean Absolute Error (*MAE*) of 0.017 for mean *DSC* and an *r* of 0.946 with an *MAE* of 0.015 for mean *JI*, indicating high consistency between predicted and true values. The proposed framework reduces reliance on manual segmentations by demonstrating robust performance of automated segmentations and enabling patient-level segmentation reliability prediction.

Keywords: Carotid intima–media thickness (CIMT), Atherosclerosis, Ultrasound, Graph Neural Network (GNN), Patient similarity graph.

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Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases are responsible for 32% of worldwide deaths (World Health Organization, 2023). The rising cases of cardiovascular conditions and increased healthcare costs have imposed a substantial economic burden (Shakya et al., 2025).

Atherosclerosis is the major cause of heart diseases, characterized by the buildup of plaques within arterial walls. As a result, the arteries become stiff and narrow, resulting in reduced blood flow (Pahwa & Jialal, 2025; Cleveland Clinic, n.d.; Mayo Clinic, n.d.). The structural difference between a normal artery and an atherosclerotic artery is shown in Fig. 1

(Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.). Atherosclerosis can cause myocardial infarction and stroke, resulting in fatality. Therefore, its detection at an early stage can prevent such issues (Sonoran Vein and Endovascular, 2024).

Figure 1. Comparison between a Normal Human Artery and an Artery Narrowed by Atherosclerotic Plaque

Source: Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.

Carotid intima–media thickness (CIMT) is a measurement of the combined thickness of the innermost two layers of the carotid artery. The two layers are the intima and media. Quantification of CIMT can aid in the early detection of vascular changes before any plaque formation (Polak et al., 2011; Bots et al., 1997; Fernández-Alvarez et al., 202). The most popular method for assessing CIMT is high-resolution B-mode ultrasound. Here, the far wall of the common carotid artery (CCA) is imaged. The far wall is usually located 1-2 cm below where the artery splits. The thickness is then determined by measuring the distance between the outer media-adventitia (MA) layer and the inner lumen-intima (LI) boundary (Stein et al., 2008; Touboul et al., 2012).

Since CIMT is strongly correlated with conventional cardiovascular risk factors like smoking, aging, dyslipidemia, diabetes, and hypertension, it is considered an important noninvasive biomarker (Lorenz et al., 2007; Naqvi & Lee, 2014; Fernández-Alvarez et al., 2025). Despite its clinical utility, CIMT

measurement is subject to several limitations. Measurements can vary due to the dependence on the operator, inconsistencies in the ultrasound equipment, and the software algorithms. Additionally, the process is time-consuming and susceptible to errors in region of interest (ROI) placement and contour detection (Faita et al., 2008; Biswas et al., 2021). Manual CIMT assessment is time-consuming and prone to error (Freire et al., 2009; AuntMinnie, n.d.).

Automated CIMT assessment has been an active area of research for over a decade. Early Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based tools, which include machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), were handmade mathematical tools that used various lumen image properties (texture, brightness, etc.) for border detection (Biswas et al., 2021; Laxminarayan, 2005; El-Baz & Suri, 2021; Biswas & Suri, 2022; Saba et al., 2019). Menchón-Lara and Sancho-Gómez (2015) developed one of the earliest fully automated ML frameworks for carotid wall boundary segmentation. Their approach exhibited reliable accuracy when applied to high-quality carotid ultrasound images. Shin et al. (2017) introduced a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based framework for automatic CIMT video analysis, including ROI localization and frame-wise segmentation. It closely matched expert manual measurements. Lainé et al. (2022) used a dilated U-Net to achieve sub-120 μm error rates across multi-center datasets. Different AI techniques for automated CIMT and plaque measurement were reviewed by Biswas et al. (2021). The need for standardization across imaging protocols and devices was highlighted to guarantee consistent and reliable results. Later Biswas et al. (2024) developed MultiNet 2.0, an efficient attention-based CNN for carotid ultrasound analysis, which improved boundary precision and generalization. The model precisely segmented the LI and MA boundaries with high accuracy. Mohammed et al. (2023) used the Carotid Ultrasound Boundary Study (CUBS) dataset to test CNN, transformer, self-organized operational neural network (self-ONN), and pixel-difference models. It was observed that transformer and pixel-difference models delivered better segmentation accuracy,

maintaining strong performance even on challenging or low-quality ultrasound scans.

Most prior studies have primarily focused on overlap-based metrics like Dice Similarity Coefficient (*DSC*) and Jaccard Index (*JI*), overlooking distance-based metrics like Point-to-Distance Metric (*PDM*) and patient risk factors like age, glucose, lipids, high blood pressure, smoking, etc. Moreover, none of the existing approaches explicitly model relational dependencies among patients or integrate clinical factors into segmentation evaluation and reliability prediction. Consequently, they fail to explain why performance varies across patient subgroups.

Figure 2. Proposed Framework for Automated CIMT Segmentation Evaluation and Reliability Prediction

In order to resolve these limitations, our study proposes a two-stage framework integrating metric-based evaluation and Graph Neural Network (GNN)-based learning for automated CIMT segmentation evaluation and reliability

prediction. The proposed framework is implemented through four sequential phases: data preprocessing, metric-based evaluation and patient-level aggregation, data normalization and feature encoding, and GNN-based learning. It is illustrated in Fig. 2.

The framework integrates clinical features and segmentation-derived metrics to model inter-patient relationships and predict segmentation performance at the patient level. Unlike traditional CNN-based methods that treat samples independently, the proposed framework captures relational patterns among similar patients, enhancing interpretability, stability, and patient-specific reliability.

Dataset Description

The CUBS dataset (Meiburger et al., 2021) was used in our study. It contains 2176 B-mode ultrasound images of both left and right CCA. These images are taken from 1,088 patients at two centers—Cyprus and Pisa (Italy). Each patient has bilateral CCA imaging done. The dataset contains three main parts. The first part contains 2,176 high-resolution grayscale images. The second part includes calibration factor (CF) (mm/pixel) data corresponding to each image. The final part comprises manual and computerized segmentations of the LI and MA boundaries in the form of coordinate points. Manual segmentations are performed by experienced sonographers, one of which is considered the gold standard. Computerized segmentations are provided by five international research groups. Additionally, the dataset provides a clinical database with 20 variables for all 1,088 patients.

Methodology

Data Preprocessing

For clinical data processing, a systematic preprocessing pipeline was applied to clean and standardize the dataset, including encoding categorical variables, converting text-based numeric variables to numeric types, validating plausible medical ranges, and imputing missing values. The resulting clinical dataset was complete and ready for analysis.

For image and segmentation mask processing, grayscale carotid ultrasound images and their corresponding CF data were loaded to convert pixel distances into millimeters. Both manual and computerized segmentation contours were used for evaluation. Each segmentation comprised paired LI and MA boundary coordinates, which were geometrically validated for consistency. Missing or malformed segmentation files were automatically skipped. An adaptive ROI was automatically determined for all images, defined as the smallest bounding box enclosing both the LI and MA contours. To remove background noise and unnecessary computational load, cropping of the images and their corresponding segmentation coordinates was done. A fixed central ROI of predefined dimensions was used for incomplete curve data cases. An outlier removal algorithm based on inter-point distance statistics was used to process each boundary for minimizing annotation noise and making contour quality better.

Figure 3. Image and Segmentation Mask Processing

Points with unusually large spacing were removed as potential annotation errors. The resulting curves were further smoothed. When minor misalignments were detected between manual and computerized curves, a centroid-based alignment correction was applied. Using polygon-filling operations, each LI-MA contour

pair was converted into a binary mask. These masks represent the arterial wall regions. They were further refined using morphological operations such as dilation and closing to ensure smooth and continuous boundaries. Both manual and computerized masks were generated in this standardized format. Fig. 3 illustrates the workflow for image and segmentation mask processing.

Metric-Based Evaluation and Patient-Level Aggregation

Evaluation metrics, i.e, *DSC*, *JI*, and *PDM*, were computed to quantitatively assess segmentation performance. For each image, the corresponding identifier and metric values were stored in a structured CSV file. These metric records were then merged with the cleaned clinical dataset using a common patient identifier (*PatientID*) extracted from the image filenames. Any entries with missing metric values were removed to ensure consistency. Finally, per-patient aggregation was performed by calculating the mean and standard deviation (*SD*) of all image-level metrics for each patient. The final aggregated dataset contained 1,088 patients and 21 variables.

Data Normalization and Feature Encoding

All continuous features were standardized before modeling. Standardization was done using z-score normalization, as expressed in Eq. (1):

$$x' = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where x' is the normalized (standardized) feature value, x is the original (raw) feature value for a given variable, μ is the mean (average) value of the feature computed across all patients in the dataset, and σ is the *SD* of the feature.

Label Encoding was used to encode categorical variables.

GNN-Based Learning

Graph Construction

To enable information sharing among clinically and algorithmically similar patients, a patient

similarity graph was constructed, where each patient corresponded to a single node. Each node contained a 38-dimensional feature vector comprising clinical variables, segmentation-derived metrics, and engineered features such as ratios and interaction terms. The Cosine similarity score between two patients i and j was computed using Eq. (2):

$$S(i, j) = \frac{x_i \cdot x_j}{\|x_i\| \|x_j\|} \quad (2)$$

where x_i and x_j are the feature vectors of patients i and j , respectively.

The dot product of the two feature vectors was computed using Eq. (3):

$$x_i \cdot x_j = \sum_{k=1}^n (x_{i,k} x_{j,k}) \quad (3)$$

where n is the total number of features, and $x_{i,k}$ and $x_{j,k}$ denote the k^{th} feature values of patients i and j , respectively.

The Euclidean norms (magnitudes) of the feature vectors were computed using Eqs. (4) and (5):

$$\|x_i\| = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n x_{i,k}^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\|x_j\| = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n x_{j,k}^2} \quad (5)$$

Each node was connected to its five most similar neighbors based on cosine similarity (top-5 $S(i, j)$), resulting in a balanced and interpretable graph structure while avoiding excessive connectivity. All edges were treated as bidirectional, allowing symmetric information flow between neighboring nodes. The resulting graph comprised 1,088 nodes and 6,288 edges, forming a robust structure for message passing. A visualization of the patient similarity graph is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Patient Similarity Graph

Architecture

Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) are neural architectures designed to operate on graph-structured data through neighborhood aggregation, commonly referred to as message passing. This mechanism enables nodes to iteratively refine their representations by integrating information from their neighbors, thereby capturing relational dependencies within the graph.

In this study, the constructed patient similarity graph served as input to a two-layer GCN. The message-passing operation in each graph convolutional layer followed the formulation proposed by Kipf and Welling (2016). For a node v , the embedding at layer k was computed using Eq. 6:

$$h_v^{(k)} = \sigma \left(W^{(k)} \sum_{u \in N(v) \cup \{v\}} \frac{h_u^{(k-1)}}{\sqrt{|N(u)| |N(v)|}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $h_u^{(k-1)}$ represents the embedding of a neighboring node u from the previous layer. The set $N(v)$ refers to the neighbors of node v , and the inclusion of v itself accounts for the addition of self-loops, allowing each node to retain its own information. The terms $|N(u)|$ and $|N(v)|$

denote the degrees of nodes u and v , respectively, and are used to perform symmetric degree normalization within the aggregation step. $W^{(k)}$ is the learnable weight matrix for layer k , and σ denotes a non-linear activation function (ReLU). This propagation rule was implemented internally by the GCNConv layers used in our model.

The proposed architecture consisted of two successive GCN layers. The first GCN layer transformed the 38-dimensional input node

features into 128-dimensional embeddings, followed by a ReLU activation and a dropout layer with a rate of 0.4 for regularization. The second GCN layer further refined the node embeddings and applied another ReLU activation. Finally, a fully connected linear layer mapped the learned node representations to a single continuous output corresponding to the predicted patient-level segmentation quality score. The overall GNN architecture is illustrated in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. GNN Architecture

Training Setup

The model was trained to predict patient-level segmentation reliability. An 80/20 train–test split was employed, resulting in 893 training patients and 195 test patients. Training was performed for 1,500 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0005 and a weight decay of 5×10^{-4} . A dropout rate of 0.4 was applied after the first GCN layer to reduce overfitting.

Predictive performance was evaluated using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Squared Error ($RMSE$) on held-out test nodes. Training and validation loss curves were monitored throughout training to ensure convergence and to detect potential overfitting.

To ensure leakage-free evaluation, the patient similarity graph was constructed exclusively from the training set. Test nodes were not connected to training nodes, and predictions for test samples were generated solely from each test node’s own features without message passing from training data.

Metrics

Metric-Based Evaluation

Both overlap-based and distance-based metrics were computed to quantitatively compare the computerized and manual segmentation masks.

DSC and JI were used to evaluate spatial correspondence between manual (A) and computerized (B) segmentation masks. They are given by Eqs. 7 and 8 respectively:

$$DSC = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|} \quad (7)$$

$$JI = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (8)$$

Two variants of PDM , i.e., LI_PDM and MA_PDM , were computed for the corresponding interfaces. The PDM value (in millimeters) is given by Eq. 9:

$$PDM = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_{manual,i} - y_{computerized,i}| \times CF \quad (9)$$

where N is the number of boundary points, $y_{manual,i}$ is the y-coordinate (pixel position) of the i^{th} point on the manual boundary line drawn by an expert, $y_{computerized,i}$ is the y-coordinate of the i^{th} corresponding point on the computerized boundary, and CF is the image-specific calibration factor (mm/pixel).

GNN Predictive Performance

The performance of the GNN was evaluated using r between predicted and actual mean metric values (e.g., mean DSC , mean JI). Complementary metrics, $RMSE$ and MAE , were also computed for absolute error estimation. The r , $RMSE$, and MAE are given by Eqs. 10, 11 and 12 respectively:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})(\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})^2}} \quad (10)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (11)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (12)$$

where y_i is the actual (true) value of the metric for the i^{th} patient, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of the metric for the i^{th} patient generated by the GNN model, \bar{y} is the mean of all actual (true) metric values in the dataset, $\bar{\hat{y}}$ is the mean of all predicted metric values, and n is the total number of patient samples (nodes) used for evaluation.

Results

Loss Curves

In Figs. 6 and 7, the GNN model's ability to predict Dice and Jaccard scores over 1,500 training epochs is demonstrated.

Figure 6. Training Convergence (Dice)

Figure 7. Training Convergence (Jaccard)

Overall Results

Metric-Based Evaluation

The overlap-based metrics were high, with a mean *DSC* of 0.915 ± 0.143 and a mean *JI* of 0.863 ± 0.158 , indicating close agreement between computerized and manual

segmentations. Boundary alignment was also within clinically acceptable limits ($LI_PDM = 0.243 \pm 0.070$ mm, $MA_PDM = 0.236 \pm 0.067$ mm), confirming the overall reliability of the segmentation process. Tables 1 and 2 summarize the performance based on overlap and distance metrics, respectively.

Table 1. Performance Summary (Overlap-Based Metrics)

Method	Mean <i>DSC</i>	<i>DSC</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Mean <i>JI</i>	<i>JI</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Type
Computerized-UCY_CY	0.9767	0.1092	0.9664	0.1131	Computerized
Manual-A3	0.9654	0.0934	0.9419	0.1008	Manual
Computerized-TUM_DE	0.9543	0.0732	0.9180	0.0803	Computerized
Computerized-INESCTEC_PT	0.9541	0.0560	0.9158	0.0700	Computerized
Manual-A1'	0.9541	0.0560	0.9158	0.0700	Manual
Manual-A1	0.9461	0.0788	0.9044	0.0938	Manual
Computerized-CNR_IT	0.9461	0.0788	0.9044	0.0938	Computerized
Manual-A2	0.8089	0.2109	0.7138	0.1991	Manual
Computerized-POLITO_IT	0.8089	0.2109	0.7138	0.1991	Computerized

Table 2. Performance Summary (Distance-Based Metrics)

Method	Mean <i>LI_PDM</i>	<i>LI_PDM</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Mean <i>MA_PDM</i>	<i>MA_PDM</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Type
Computerized-UCY_CY	0.2626	0.0722	0.2632	0.0689	Computerized
Manual-A3	0.2082	0.0787	0.2137	0.0738	Manual
Computerized-TUM_DE	0.1546	0.0369	0.1694	0.0366	Computerized
Computerized-INESCTEC_PT	0.2231	0.0505	0.2094	0.0440	Computerized
Manual-A1'	0.2231	0.0505	0.2094	0.0440	Manual
Manual-A1	0.2668	0.0570	0.2608	0.0577	Manual
Computerized-CNR_IT	0.2668	0.0570	0.2608	0.0577	Computerized
Manual-A2	0.2621	0.0744	0.2517	0.0746	Manual
Computerized-POLITO_IT	0.2621	0.0744	0.2517	0.0746	Computerized

GNN Predictive Performance

The GNN model exhibited exceptional predictive capability, achieving an *r* of 0.972 for mean *DSC* and 0.946 for mean *JI*. These near-perfect correlations indicate that the GNN successfully captured the nonlinear dependencies governing segmentation quality. Quantitative results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Quantitative Results

Target Metric	<i>r</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>
Mean <i>DSC</i>	0.972	0.017	0.022
Mean <i>JI</i>	0.946	0.015	0.020

Error Analysis

As shown in Fig 8, the *PDM* error distributions for the *LI* and *MA* interfaces are unimodal and concentrated around 0.22–0.25 mm, demonstrating stable sub-millimeter precision in boundary localization.

The cumulative distributions in Fig. 9 indicate that about 90% of cases have deviations < 0.3 mm, confirming consistent segmentation accuracy across subjects. The *MA* curve is slightly left-shifted, suggesting a marginally lower boundary error compared to the *LI* interface.

Figure 8. PDM Error Distribution (LI vs. MA)

Figure 9. Cumulative Distribution of LI and MA Errors

The CIMT error distribution (MA - LI) in Fig. 10 is centered near zero (mean = -0.007 mm), indicating negligible bias between the two interfaces and excellent agreement of automated wall localization.

Fig. 11 compares the absolute boundary errors of the LI and MA interfaces, showing nearly identical distributions and reinforcing the robustness of the segmentation algorithm.

Figure 10. CIMT Error Distribution (MA-LI)

Figure 11. Absolute Boundary Errors of LI and MA Interfaces

Figure 12 Absolute Error Distribution for Dice

Figure 13 Absolute Error Distribution for Jaccard

As shown in Fig. 12, the distribution is sharply centered around zero, with an MAE of 0.0165, indicating that most predicted Dice scores

closely match their true values. The narrow spread confirms high prediction accuracy and minimal bias.

In Fig. 13, the Jaccard error distribution shows a similar trend, with a marginally lower MAE of 0.0153, indicating stable, consistent, and well-generalized predictions across patients. The GNN model's robustness is further confirmed by the steep decline toward higher errors.

Visualization of LI-MA Boundary Segmentation

Fig. 14 illustrates an example showing the selected ROI in a carotid ultrasound image with manual LI and MA boundaries compared to computerized LI and MA boundaries.

Figure 14. LI-MA Boundary Segmentation

Summary of Findings

Metric-based evaluation across multiple computerized methods demonstrated high segmentation performance (mean $DSC = 0.915 \pm 0.143$, mean $JI = 0.863 \pm 0.158$) and clinically excellent boundary agreement ($LI_PDM = 0.243 \pm 0.070$ mm, $MA_PDM = 0.236 \pm 0.067$ mm), confirming sub-millimeter precision and reliability. Patient-level aggregation of clinical features and segmentation-derived metrics helped in the stabilization of measurements and minimization of noise. This led to robust features for GNN-based learning.

The GNN obtained near-perfect agreement between predicted and true segmentation quality, with $r = 0.972$ for mean DSC and $r = 0.946$ for mean JI while maintaining very low MAE (≤ 0.017). The network effectively learned nonlinear dependencies and propagated contextual information between clinically similar patients.

Segmentation-derived metrics exerted a greater impact on quality prediction than individual clinical features. This confirmed that algorithmic stability, rather than physiological variability, is the dominant determinant of segmentation reliability.

Overall, the proposed framework bridges advanced GNN-based learning with classical metric-based evaluation. Its ability to predict segmentation quality with high correlation and sub-millimeter accuracy supports dependable, automated quality control and reduces the dependence on manual review in large-scale vascular ultrasound studies.

Statistical Analysis

In Fig. 15, points are clustered tightly around the ideal fit line. This validates the accuracy of the prediction. We can see similar linear alignment in Fig. 16. The GNN predicted overlap-based metrics with high accuracy: for mean DSC , $r = 0.972$ and $MAE = 0.017$, and for mean JI , $r = 0.946$ and $MAE = 0.015$. Scatter points lie tightly along the identity line—particularly in the clinically important 0.7–1.0 range—indicating reliable reproduction of high-quality segmentations with typical errors of only ~1.5–1.7 percentage points.

Figure 15. Dice Regression Plot

Figure 16. Jaccard Regression Plot

Discussion

Comparison with Existing Automated CIMT Approaches

Recent advances in automated CIMT analysis have mainly focused on convolutional and transformer-based models for boundary segmentation and measurement. Approaches such as the dilated U-Nets by Lainé et al. (2022), along with the attention-driven MultiNet 2.0 by Biswas et al. (2024), achieved high boundary precision in carotid wall segmentation, but remained sensitive to image quality and scanner variability. Likewise, Mohammed et al. (2023) discovered that transformer and pixel-difference models maintain strong performance even on noisy ultrasound scans, yet they are constrained to pixel-level processing and lack integration of broader clinical information.

Compared to these prior CNN-based or intensity-driven methods, the present framework introduces a two-stage hybrid design: a metric-based evaluation stage that provides deterministic, clinically interpretable segmentation evaluation (mean $DSC = 0.915 \pm 0.143$, mean $JI = 0.863 \pm 0.158$, $LI_PDM \approx 0.239 \pm 0.070$ mm, $MA_PDM \approx 0.236 \pm 0.067$ mm), and a GNN-based learning stage that learns patient-wise relational dependencies and

enhances interpretability ($r = 0.972$ for mean DSC , $r = 0.946$ for mean JI , $MAE \leq 0.017$).

Unlike existing models, this work integrates metric-based evaluation, and GNN-based learning, establishing a reliable computational system capable of quantifying both image-level and patient-level reliability. Thus, the proposed framework bridges the interpretability of overlap- and distance-based metrics with the generalization strength of GNN-based learning, outperforming traditional CNN frameworks in consistency and clinical correlation.

Integrated Evaluation of the metric-based evaluation and GNN-based learning Framework

The initial metric-based evaluation established a reliable foundation for assessing segmentation performance, with high overlap-based metrics (mean $DSC = 0.915 \pm 0.143$, mean $JI = 0.863 \pm 0.158$) and sub-millimeter boundary precision ($LI_PDM \approx 0.239 \pm 0.070$ mm, $MA_PDM \approx 0.236 \pm 0.067$ mm). These results confirmed that computerized CIMT measurements closely matched expert annotations. The proposed framework broadened the analysis by modeling patient-level relationships using a patient similarity graph integrating clinical features and segmentation-derived metrics. The GNN achieved strong predictive performance ($r = 0.972$ for mean DSC , $r = 0.946$ for mean JI , $MAE \leq 0.017$), demonstrating its ability to capture inter-patient dependencies and improve prediction consistency. Metric-based evaluation and GNN-based learning work together to form a complementary framework that combines interpretability and quantitative accuracy for a reliable and clinically valid CIMT segmentation evaluation and reliability prediction.

Clinical Interpretations and Implications

The proposed framework shows that automated segmentation can achieve sub-millimeter accuracy, comparable to manual segmentation. Large epidemiological cohorts, routine screening, and AI-assisted tele-ultrasound workflows can all benefit from the scalable deployment of such precision. The computerized system mitigates demographic bias by performing consistently across patient

subgroups. The GNN improves clinical trust in AI-assisted vascular imaging by validating segmentation quality and ensuring fair, patient-agnostic performance.

Limitations and Future Work

While the proposed framework demonstrates strong performance, several limitations merit discussion. The dataset used was limited to specific acquisition protocols and imaging centers; hence, extension to multi-institutional data from varied ultrasound scanners is required to confirm cross-device robustness. Moreover, the current cosine similarity-based graph construction captures linear relationships but may overlook non-linear or temporal dependencies. To better depict complex inter-patient relationships, future work could use attention-based dynamic graphs or learned adjacency matrices.

The present framework operates on static 2D images. Integrating spatio-temporal GNNs could enable longitudinal tracking of CIMT progression and richer vascular modeling. Furthermore, explainable AI tools could improve model transparency and clinical trust even though correlation-based interpretability was explored. Finally, real-time deployment within ultrasound scanners and integration into clinical workflows remain essential next steps to assess operational feasibility and real-world impact.

Summary

In summary, this study shows that computerized CIMT measurements can reach an accuracy level similar to expert manual assessments, supported by the strong consistency observed in key evaluation metrics such as *DSC*, *JI*, and *PDM*. The proposed framework provides robust, patient-level predictions of segmentation reliability by successfully combining clinical features and segmentation-derived metrics. By modeling inter-patient relationships through relational learning, the framework improves both interpretability and generalization, offering a deeper understanding of segmentation performance across diverse patient profiles. Ultimately, this integration of traditional metric-based evaluation with GNN-based learning

narrows the gap between automated image analysis and real-world clinical reasoning, contributing toward the development of transparent, dependable, and clinically meaningful AI tools in vascular imaging.

Conclusion

This work offers a robust and interpretable framework for automated CIMT segmentation evaluation and reliability prediction by integrating metric-based evaluation with GNN-based learning. The metric-based evaluation achieved high segmentation performance (mean *DSC* = 0.915 ± 0.143 , mean *JI* = 0.863 ± 0.158) and sub-millimeter boundary precision (*LI_PDM* $\approx 0.239 \pm 0.070$ mm, *MA_PDM* $\approx 0.236 \pm 0.067$ mm), validating the reliability of computerized methods against expert manual annotations. The framework achieved strong predictive alignment ($r = 0.972$ for mean *DSC*, $r = 0.946$ for mean *JI*, $MAE \leq 0.017$) and improved consistency across patients by combining clinical features with segmentation-derived metrics using a GNN. These outcomes demonstrate that computerized CIMT assessment can serve as a clinically dependable and scalable alternative to manual measurement, advancing patient-specific and trustworthy AI applications in cardiovascular diagnostics. Unlike conventional CNN-based approaches, the proposed model effectively captures global patient-level dependencies, reduces variability, and enhances prediction stability. It creates a reliable pathway toward automated, transparent, and clinically meaningful CIMT segmentation evaluation by maintaining sub-millimeter geometric accuracy and providing insights that can be clinically interpreted. Future directions involve extending the framework to multi-center datasets, incorporating temporal GNNs for longitudinal vascular tracking, and integrating explainable AI tools for real-time clinical deployment.

Statements and Declarations

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Competing Interests

The authors affirm that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Author Contributions

Pratik Timilsina: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization. Rajesh Dahal: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization. Mahendra Kumar Gourisaria: Supervision. Mainak Biswas: Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation.

Data Availability

The publicly available CUBS dataset (Meiburger et al., 2021) was used for this study.

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